

EASY WAYS TO MEMORIZE VOCABULARIES

S.Axmedova

Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute

4th stage student

ABSTRACT: As we all know, in our now rapidly growing world, English is the most globalized language. We cannot learn a language effectively without a strong foundation in vocabulary and grammar. In this case, learning new words can be very difficult, particularly, when you see many words you don't know. However, with the right approaches, you can easily remember words and expand your language skills. This article is about how learners can memorize new vocabularies with easy and effective way without spending much time. Specifically, if you're a new language learner, a student or young teacher who wants to teach your students some tips, these easy-to-implement strategies will help you.

Key words: word memorization methods, long-term memory, short-term memory, flashcards, mnemonics, conceptual understanding, combination methods.

"The limits of my language are the limits of my world." - Ludwig Wittgenstein.¹ Nowadays, learning foreign languages is becoming popular among young adults. Everyone learns a foreign language to achieve various goals, such as studying abroad, travelling, pursuing a career. So, acquiring vocabulary is

1. ¹ Sterling, L.C. (2014). *'The limits of my language mean the limits of my world.'* [online] Medium.
<https://medium.com/@lcsterling/the-limits-of-my-language-mean-the-limits-of-my-world-68b94fc1d119>.

essential part of language learning. Just think about it. How it could be master language with only grammar and sentence structure without knowing its meaning? Every new word learned is another ticket towards making themselves understood. Although, they will face some issues during this period. One of the biggest challenges in learning any foreign language is memorization. This process involves learning not just dozens or hundreds, but thousands of new words.

The main reason for this problem is the use of outdated methods for memorizing words, such as the repetition method. Words memorized using this method for a certain period of time will eventually be forgotten. In order to easily memorize new words, effectively use them in communication, and retain them in memory for a longer duration, it is crucial to employ new and efficient memorization techniques.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Here are some ways to solve this problem.

1-method. Combination - create connecting networks. Brain takes in what read and converts it into images, ideas, and feelings, and then makes connections between the new information and what already know. The process of remembering is like this - the new merges with the old. When people associate a new word or concept with what they already know, it becomes easier for the brain to find and remember in time. 2

² Xolmatova, S. (2021). *INGLIZ TILIDAGI SO'ZLARNI YODLASHNING 7 SAMARALI USULI*. [online] FLEDU.UZ. Available at: <https://fledu.uz/uz/ingliz-tilidagi-sozlarni-yodlashning-7-samarali-usuli>

For example: beverages, fruits, clothes, furniture, greetings, places .

For instance: furniture: armchair, table, cabinet, bed, folding table.

2-method. Visually recalling information. The brain reads visual information better. Use colored markers, felt-tip pens, and stickers. Passages to be remembered are marked with a chosen color or other visual cue. For example, to quickly memorize the text in English, it needs to draw or stick pictures that match the meaning of each paragraph. The funnier picture makes more interesting and memorable the process.³

3-method. Creating stories. Imagine a funny and absurd story that includes all the words you're trying to remember. The more ridiculous the story, the better you'll remember it. By combining these words in a humorous way, learner will find it easier to recall them later.⁴

4-method. Use flashcards (in moderation!). Some teachers say they're an effective way to learn small facts in bulk. Others say that learning words with

³ <https://daryo.uz/2022/08/26/malumotlarni-qanday-qilib-tezda-yodlash-mumkin-eng-samarali-va-sinalgan-layfxaklar>

⁴ <https://fledu.uz/uz/ingliz-tilidagi-sozlarni-yodlashning-7-samarali-usuli>

flashcards means removing them from their contexts, and often causes important layers of meaning to be lost. Flashcards are very useful tools. If learner just starting out, he or she certainly have a place in their language-learning toolkit. This said, make sure to practice whatever words you learn with flashcards in different situations as soon as you can.

There are many free flashcard apps available to use on phone. With these, learner learn a few new vocabulary words anytime get a spare moment.

For example: Quizlet. It's a flashcard app with smart features and it can handle images, diagrams, various languages, and even audio uploads, so it's ideal for self-paced learning and studying. Students can have fun with studying by using the game formats that Quizlet has to offer.

5-method. Try learning example sentences. Another point about the importance of learning words in context! Sometimes words are used completely differently in practice than might think. For example, when taking journeys by train or bus, many native English speakers, in practice, use the verb “to catch.” It is common to hear sentences such as: I catch the bus at 7:30 every weekday. We’re catching an overnight train.

If students learned the verb “to catch” as a single word, they might describe it as “to receive and hold, or to capture.” This definition is correct! But learning this and nothing else would make a common sentence like the one above sound extremely odd to listener. That’s why lots of people swear by a technique called “sentence mining” — learning lists of full sentences. Fans claim that it makes them able to use new vocabulary faster since they memorize its grammar and common use cases from the start.⁵

6-method: Use mnemonics. Mnemonics are a memorization technique that many people swear by. A mnemonic is a strange image or a story that learners

⁵ <https://preply.com/en/blog/how-to-memorize-new-words-in-english>

make to help them remember a word and its meaning. For example, if learners were trying to remember the Spanish verb, “to fit” — “caber” — they might picture a man trying to fit a bear into the passenger seat of a cab (or taxi). In that bizarre mental image, they have the two sounds that need to remember “cab” and “ber”, along with the meaning of the word “to fit” The stranger and sillier the image, the more likely it is to stick in brain. Mnemonics require a little bit of imagination to come up with, but they are astonishingly effective! 6

Memory is a part of the human mind. It involves the cognitive activity of retaining and recalling past experiences, events, and information. Memory holds great importance in language learning. It is responsible for storing words, rules, pronunciations, and all newly acquired knowledge. "Memory techniques' most crucial area of practical assistance is, in my opinion, the retention of vocabulary," said Shohruh Mirzo Rahmonov.

It can be observed that memory not only aids in memorizing words but also reinforces the strengthening of memory itself. There are two types of memory: short-term memory and long-term memory. Short-term memory retains information for a short period and then discards it. The downside of short-term memory is that information can quickly vanish from memory. To prevent this, the information that needs to be remembered should be repeated or given focused attention for around 7 seconds between periods.

Long-term memory, on the other hand, is the type of memory that stores information for an extended duration. If a person attaches more significance, attention, and awareness to the information, it will be stored in long-term memory. The availability of various methods for memorizing words illustrates the transfer of memorized information from short-term to long-term memory.

⁶ <https://preply.com/en/blog/how-to-memorize-new-words-in-english>

Mnemonics play a primary role in transferring information to long-term memory.

The word "mnemonics" is derived from the Greek word "Mnemosyne," which means memory. Mnemonika is the technique of memorizing difficult words easily. It encompasses various techniques that help in storing and retaining a large number of words and information in a short period of time. Additionally, by adding additional meanings and imagining the word, one can also remember the word itself.

There are four characteristics of memory: location, association, imagination, and repetition. The location characteristic is when we associate something we want to remember with a specific location, making it easier to retain. For e, when a person hears a song for the first time, they may remember where they first heard it or what state they were in. Utilizing location association is beneficial when it comes to remembering a specific word. We start by selecting five locations in our house and then select five words that need to be remembered. For example:

1. Cupboard - Apple
2. Television - Mercury
3. Sofa - Watermelon
4. Refrigerator - Hand
5. Clock - Robot

Now, using the location characteristic and mnemonic, each word is associated with its location. How can we connect an apple with a cupboard? With imagination, we visualize the cupboard full of apples. Mercury and television. Information about the planets originating from Mercury is being shared on the television. Sofa and watermelon. The watermelon is placed on the sofa and is being crushed. Refrigerator and hand. The refrigerator has hands and is dancing. Clock and robot. Various robots are sitting on the clock and having a conversation with each other. Now, each piece of furniture in the house is connected to a specific item: a cupboard full of apples, a television sharing information about

Mercury, a sofa with a squashed watermelon, a refrigerator with dancing hands, and a clock with robots. Connecting the item with its location helps improve memory and cognitive abilities.

Association is the second most essential characteristic of memory. It is the connection between two things. For example, when we mention the word "lazgi," it undoubtedly invokes associations with Khorezm, or the words "sariy" and "deli holiday" invoke thoughts of India. Association is the process of relating new information to existing knowledge. For example, the word "feel" in English has a similar pronunciation to "fil" in Uzbek. To make it easier to remember, these two words can be combined, meaning that the main character in the influential movie felt like an elephant and burst into laughter. The more vivid or unusual the association, the easier and longer it will be retained in memory.

Imagination. When we hear a word, the ability to imagine it is another characteristic of memory. Let's take the word "divan" as an example. When we mention the word "divan," various images of a big, soft, or reclining piece of furniture come to mind. The English translation of this word is "sofa." Now, let's visualize it: a soft sofa, a big sofa, a new sofa. This method allows us to associate the new word with an imaginary translation and store it in our memory.

Repetition is another way to enhance memory. When information is repeated in an organized manner, it helps to retain it in memory for a longer period. There are different types of repetition. Scheduled repetition involves revisiting the information after an hour, a day, a week, or a month. This is like charging and keeping the information active in the memory.

In addition to scheduled repetition, there is another type called spaced repetition. It takes into account a 96-hour interval. Every four days, the memorized information is revisited to prevent it from fading away. The human brain retains information for about four days, and if it's not revisited within that time frame, there's a possibility of forgetting it. So, if the words are revisited once

every four days after being memorized, those words will remain in the memory for a longer period.⁷

Learners across the world can be broadly classified into two types – one, people who learn to understand and two, people who learn to remember or recalls. The people in the first category understand the concept, while the latter merely memorize the concepts to be able to recall it later. While memorizing helps commit to the memory, understanding the concept helps us gain knowledge and appreciate our education.

When you understand a concept, you will remember it for years whereas when you memorize the same, you will remember it for merely for days and gradually forget it. Conceptual understanding helps you understand the information on a deeper level unlike memorizing which merely touches the surface. Marketing concepts for instance, need to be understood to be able to apply practically. If you memorize marketing concepts, you might pass your exams but you won't know how to apply them unless you understand the crux of the concept.

Another advantage of conceptual understanding is it helps you grow as a person and shift your perception. This is impossible with memorizing. When you understand concepts you are able to connect it with other concepts, compare it with other concepts and generate creative ideas and apply the concept to real life situations. Whereas memorizing won't help you achieve any of this.

⁷ <https://oriens.uz/uz/journal/article/yangi-soz-yodlashning-samarali-usullari/>

Theory:

Practice:

Memorizing is helpful if you want to recall information at a specific given time. Memorizing helps you remember concepts. Whereas if you understand a concept you will not only be able to remember it for long, but also put it in your own words whenever you want and also explain it to others. Memorizing limits the memorized content to 'recall', whereas understanding the concept helps in generating creative ideas.⁸

Naturally, students need to see and hear words to learn them. The number of exposures needed depends on the learner and ranges from 5 to 20. Generally, 8 to 10 exposures are necessary for you to have a good chance of recognizing and understanding a new word later on. In order to both understand and be able to use those new words, more exposure is needed. To get more exposure, reading is a great activity because it is likely to see the same words appear multiple times in the text that be read⁹.

"Word memorization consists of two stages. 1. Getting acquainted with the

⁸ Oliveboard. (2016). *Conceptual Understanding vs Memorizing*.

word. 2. Starting to use it, which means exploitation. If we imagine word memorization as a complete circle, then getting acquainted would be until halfway through the circle, and after actively using it, we reach the end of the circle. The second part is crucial."

Some important aspects to consider in word memorization are:

Choosing correct words. A study by Mark Davies, a corpus linguist, suggests that an average adult native English speaker knows around 20,000 to 35,000 words. Another study by Mark Davies found that the average person uses around 2,000 to 3,000 words in their daily conversations. therefore, the learner should be careful in choosing words when memorizing words.

Taking breaks. It is crucial in the process of word memorization. This process doesn't happen all at once. It requires time for the language to be better internalized and for words to be effectively retained. Therefore, it is necessary to go through the process without putting pressure in order to make it more fruitful.

Proper nutrition. Some foods can have both health and memory benefits, as well as potential harm. It is important to adhere to a proper nutrition regimen.

Stimulate interest. There is no secret that if someone has a genuine interest, the information tends to stick better. Therefore, look for methods that provide an easy way to learn English, such as TV series, books, podcasts, songs, and others.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the process of memorizing words absolutely requires strong and effective techniques. The methods and recommendations mentioned above are its solution. Considering that everyone's learning ability varies, it is necessary to not rely on just one method, but choose several methods that are more effective. In the modern era of technology, it is possible to solve problems through various applications and websites. It is crucial to say, the important part is not only memorizing words but also using them in real life.

REFERENCES

Shohruh Mirzo Rahmonov va Iskandar Sattibayev “So’z yodlash sirlari”. Toshkent 2015, “Istiqlol nuri” nashriyot

Sterling, L.C. (2014). ‘The limits of my language mean the limits of my world.’ [online] Medium. Available at: <https://medium.com/@lcsterling/the-limits-of-my-language-mean-the-limits-of-my-world-68b94fc1d119>.

oriens.uz. (n.d.). YANGI SO’Z YODLASHNING SAMARALI USULLARI - ORIENS. [online] Available at: <https://oriens.uz/uz/journal/article/yangi-soz-yodlashning-samarali-usullari/> [Accessed 1 Aug. 2024]

Xolmatova, S. (2021). INGLIZ TILIDAGI SO’ZLARNI YODLASHNING 7 SAMARALI USULI. [online] FLEDU.UZ. Available at: <https://fledu.uz/uz/ingliz-tilidagi-sozlarni-yodlashning-7-samarali-usuli/> [Accessed 1 Aug. 2024].

Ma’lumotlarni qanday qilib tezda yodlash mumkin: eng samarali va sinalgan layfxaklar. [online] Daryo.uz. Available at: <https://daryo.uz/2022/08/26/malumotlarni-qanday-qilib-tezda-yodlash-mumkin-eng-samarali-va-sinalgan-layfxaklar> [Accessed 1 Aug. 2024].

preply.com. (2015). How To Memorize Vocabulary: 10 Tips To Learn & Remember New Words. [online] Available at: <https://preply.com/en/blog/how-to-memorize-new-words-in-english/>.

Oliveboard. (2016). Conceptual Understanding vs Memorizing. [online] Available at: <https://www.oliveboard.in/blog/conceptual-understanding-vs-memorizing/#:~:text=While%20memorizing%20helps%20commit%20to.>

Anon, (n.d.). 5 Research-Based Facts About Vocabulary Learning to Help You Learn Faster | EnglishClub.com. [online] Available at: <https://www.englishclub.com/efl/articles/vocabulary/learn-faster/> [Accessed 1 Aug. 2024]